

Spectrophotometric study of a charge transfer complex of 4-acetamidophenol with 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone in pure ethanol medium[†]

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Abstract : 2,3-Dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone has been found to form a charge transfer complex with 4-acetamidophenol (paracetamol). The charge transfer band has been located and the formation constant value at different temperatures have been measured by using the Benesi-Hildebrand equation modified for a 2 : 1 complex. Thermodynamic quantities, the enthalpy and entropy of formation of the complex have been obtained from the temperature dependence data. The sign and magnitude of these quantities have been discussed.

Keywords : 2,3-Dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone, paracetamol, charge transfer or electron donor-acceptor complex, 2 : 1 complex, enthalpy and entropy of complex formation.

Introduction

The existence of molecular complexes has been recognized since long time¹ and understanding their formation in terms of acid-base theory² had also been provided long ago. But the subject matter has begun to draw interest since 1949 with the observation of Hildebrand³ of a new absorption band in the ultraviolet spectrum of a solution of iodine in benzene which was characteristic of a complex. The historic interpretation by Mulliken⁴ in a quantum-theoretical form has laid the foundation of the theory of this type of molecular complex, commonly known as "electron donor-acceptor" or "charge-transfer complex". Since then, quite a good number of review articles written by well known workers in the field appeared⁵⁻⁷, laying emphasis on various aspects of the subject matter.

EDA complexes occur in a wide variety of systems and have found a variety of applications in biological systems. The action of a drug in a biological system is ultimately the result of physicochemical interactions^{8,9} between the drug molecule and the functionally important molecules known as the "receptors" present in living systems^{10,11}. Birks and Slifkin¹² have shown the impor-

tance of quinones as models in many biochemical reactions in living systems.

The present communication reports the results of spectroscopic and thermodynamic studies of EDA interaction of paracetamol (4-acetamidophenol), a common antipyretic drug, with 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone in ethanol medium. The structures of the drug molecule (paracetamol) and the quinone are shown in Fig. 1. The lone pairs of electrons of oxygen and nitrogen and the aromatic ring make paracetamol a potential electron donor. It is to be noted that whereas most of the study of EDA complexes are reported¹³ in non-polar solvents such as CCl₄, CHCl₃

Fig. 1. Structures of (a) 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone and (b) 4-acetamidophenol (paracetamol).

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

etc., the medium used in the present study is ethanol, a solvent which is more environment-friendly and more useful as a medium of studying biochemical processes than the usual non-polar solvents mentioned above. The study, therefore, is expected to have some relevance in physical pharmacy.

Experimental

2,3-Dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone and 4-acetamidophenol (paracetamol) were a Sigma and an Aldrich product respectively. Their purity was checked by melting point determination and was used without further purification. Ethanol was dried over lime and distilled. The distillate was refluxed for half an hour with iodine activated Mg and then distilled under moisture free conditions.

The purified solvents were kept in thermostat for equilibration to the desired temperature. Stock solutions of 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone (acceptor) were prepared using these solvents and were kept at the same temperature. A series of weighed quantities of paracetamol (donor) were taken in different volumetric flasks, a constant volume of the acceptor solution was added to each of these weighed quantities of the donor and the total volume was made up to a constant volume (10 ml) by adding appropriate volumes of the thermally equilibrated solvent.

The spectra of the solutions at various temperatures were recorded by using a Shimadzu UV1601 PC model spectrophotometer equipped with Peltier-controlled thermostatic bath.

Results and discussion

Paracetamol in ethanol medium does not absorb in the visible range. The absorption spectrum of 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone ($3.27 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in ethanol medium is given in Fig. 2 together with those of mixtures containing the two compounds in ethanol medium. A broad CT absorption band centered at 452 nm was observed for each mixture.

The well known Benesi-Hildebrand³ equation for 1 : 1 stoichiometry is used to evaluate its equilibrium constant k of the reaction for complex formation from spectrophotometric data,

$$lC_A^0/d_c = 1/K\epsilon_c \cdot 1/C_D^0 + 1/\epsilon_c \quad (1)$$

where l is the optical path length, C_A^0 and C_D^0 are the initial concentration of the acceptor and the donor respectively, ϵ_c is the molar absorptivity of the complex and $d_c = d$ is the observed absorbance of the mixture (i.e. mixture of the complex and the uncomplexed donor and the acceptor in this case). By using the acceptor solution as reference, the observed absorbance d is considered as the absorbance of the mixture, since the donor does not absorb at the wavelength of measurement.

Fig. 2. Increase in intensity of the CT absorption band of the complex 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone with 4-acetamidophenol with increase in concentration of the latter. Spectra corresponding to concentration sets in Table 1 have been shown. Reference : acceptor solutions, temp. = 298 K. In the ordinate, 'Abs.' Means 'absorbance'.

But the Benesi-Hildebrand plot of lC_A^0/d_c against $1/C_D^0$, according to the eq. (1) yielded a wide scatter in the plots of experimental data and the correlation was not satisfactory. However, reasonably good linear plots were obtained by using the following modified version of the Benesi-Hildebrand³ equation for cells with 1 cm path length and complexes of 2 : 1 stoichiometry :

$$\frac{[A]_0[D]_0^2}{d'} = \frac{[D]_0^2}{\epsilon'} + \frac{1}{K\epsilon'} \quad (2)$$

The symbols have their usual meanings. The only quantity with some difference is ϵ' . It is defined as $\epsilon' = \epsilon_c - \epsilon_A - 2\epsilon_D$ and it means the apparent molar absorptivity of the complex, ϵ_A and ϵ_D being those of the acceptor and the donor respectively at λ_{CT} . The coefficient 2 of ϵ_D is due to the 2 : 1 stoichiometry.

Experimental data are given in Tables 1 and 2. Very good linear plots according to eq. (2) were obtained for the complex under study. A typical plot is shown in Fig.

3. The correlation coefficients of all such plots were above 0.98. Values of K of the complex and the apparent molar absorptivities (ϵ') obtained from such plots are shown in Table 2. The experimental data were also subjected to the equation derived by Seal *et al.*¹³. The enthalpies of formation were obtained using van't Hoff equation. Plots of $\ln K$ against $1/T$ is shown in Fig. 4 which follows the following regression equation,

$$\ln K = (1894 \pm 44)/T + (-2.69 \pm 0.14) \quad (3)$$

Correlation coefficient is 0.999. The values of enthalpy (ΔH_f^0) and entropy (ΔS_f^0) of formation obtained from such plots are given in Table 2. Both ΔH_f^0 and ΔS_f^0 were found to be negative. Similar results were also obtained and explained in our earlier studies¹⁴ of charge transfer interaction between menadione (Vitamin K₃) with a series of phenols.

Physicochemical properties of a drug molecule in solution determine the mechanism of action of the drug. Investigation of spectroscopic and thermodynamic proper-

Table 1. Absorbance data of mixtures containing 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone (acceptor) and 4-acetamidophenol (paracetamol) (donor) in water medium at five different temperatures against the pristine acceptor solution as references

10^3 [2,3-Dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10 \times$ [Paracetamol] (mol dm ⁻³) [in ethanol]	Absorbance at 452 nm				
		293 K	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
3.271	1.340	0.0956	0.0938	0.0825	0.0773	0.0707
	1.441	0.0924	0.0920	0.0862	0.0814	0.0785
	1.616	0.1047	0.0990	0.0967	0.0912	0.0889
	1.777	0.1108	0.1067	0.1038	0.1007	0.0961
	1.958	0.1196	0.1191	0.1160	0.1101	0.1063
3.271	2.104	0.1299	0.1279	0.1235	0.1200	0.1132
	2.247	0.1379	0.1361	0.1313	0.1249	0.1202
	2.415	0.1453	0.1451	0.1394	0.1349	0.1292

Table 2. Formation constants, enthalpy and entropy of formation of the complex of 4-acetamidophenol with 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone in ethanol medium

Medium	Temp. (K)	Formation constant (K) (mol ⁻¹ dm ³)	ΔH_f^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_f^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Pure ethanol	293	44 ± 0.4		
	298	39 ± 0.7		
	303	35 ± 0.4	-15.7 ± 0.4	-22.3 ± 0.1
	308	32 ± 0.2		
	313	29 ± 1.6		

ties of drug molecules is of importance in pharmacokinetics¹⁵. Spectroscopic and thermodynamic investigation also lead to a measure of the strength of binding of the drug molecules to other substances present in living systems. It was indicated much earlier by Webb and Thompson¹⁶ that electron donor-acceptor complexes possibly have some role in drug-receptor binding. For a molecule to act as an acceptor, it should have an electron-attracting part. A quinoid ring has this property and it is common to many biomolecules.

Fig. 3. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for 4-acetamidophenol (paracetamol) with 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone complex in pure ethanol medium at 303 K.

Fig. 4. van't Hoff plots for complexes of 4-acetamidophenol with 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone.

Conclusion :

The present study shows that 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone forms charge transfer complex with 4-acetamidophenol (i.e. paracetamol) in ethanol medium. The stoichiometry of the complex is 2 : 1 (paracetamol : 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone) and the formation of the complex is reversible ($2D + A \rightleftharpoons D_2A$), so that

van't Hoff equation holds, yielding the heat and entropy of complexation. The order of magnitude of heat of formation is similar to those of typical CT complexes as reported in relevant references¹⁷. The entropy of complexation, ΔS_f^0 , is negative, indicating that the process is associative and that not much desolvation of the donor or acceptor occurs during complexation.

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